

SAFE USE OF LITHIUM-ION BATTERIES: OECD EXPERIENCE - SOME RECOMMENDATIONS FOR VIETNAM**Pham Tien Dung**

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Abstract

Safety is one of the most important consumer rights according to the guidelines of the international consumer organization CI as well as in the Law on Consumer Protection 2024 of Vietnam. Normally, when talking about safety for consumers, they often think of safety in buying goods and services to serve daily eating needs, often associated with food such as: clean food, organic food, food without preservatives, food without additives, not raised for growth... That is completely true, however, safety for consumers does not stop at safety in buying and using products to serve daily eating needs but also in safety in purchasing other products, goods and services. In today's article, we would like to share the content of the campaign "Global awareness campaign on lithium-ion battery product safety" in 2024 of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development - OECD, from which we make some recommendations for Vietnam.

Keywords: Consumer, products, goods, individual trading goods and services Organizational responsibility, lithium-ion batteries

1. Some content related to the use of lithium-ion batteries

With a history of more than 200 years, up to now, batteries are a popular energy source for many personal devices, household appliances and industrial applications. Lithium-ion batteries (abbreviated as li-ion) are a type of rechargeable battery with an important component of lithium ion acting as an electrolyte between the two battery poles. Lithium-ion batteries are a type of rechargeable battery, widely used in personal electronic devices such as phones, laptops, smart wearable devices, electric vehicles and many other applications. This is a type of reusable battery, capable of storing and supplying electrical energy by moving lithium ions between two electrodes (anode and cathode) during charging. Although lithium-ion batteries are widely used in familiar consumer devices with many benefits such as: long life, light weight, stable power supply, high flexibility, many consumers are still not fully aware of the potential risks that this type of battery can cause when exposed to high temperatures as well as the classification and treatment of batteries after their expiration date. Having a clear understanding of product information as well as how to use the product safely is very important to protect yourself, those around you and the living environment of the community. Along with the explosion of the 4.0 revolution and technological innovation, the production of electrical and electronic devices has grown strongly, the demand for changing electrical and electronic products is increasing, leading to a large increase in the amount of electronic waste. Vietnam is no exception when the amount of electronic waste including lithium-ion batteries in the country is increasing rapidly, creating pressure on the treatment of this special type of waste. The safe production and consumption as well as the responsibility of relevant parties in the treatment of industrial waste, specifically lithium ion batteries, are raising many issues of concern for the whole society. Used batteries are causing people to have headaches in dealing with them. Because waste batteries are not ordinary waste,

they contain many chemicals that are harmful to health. Batteries cannot be thrown into the trash with other types of waste but need to be collected and treated separately. If not classified and disposed of properly, they will become a hazard to the environment and human health. Batteries often contain heavy metals such as lead, mercury, cadmium and arsenic... which are all extremely toxic substances, dangerous to the brain, kidneys, cardiovascular system and human fertility

To have a correct understanding of how to use, store, recycle and dispose of batteries, as well as establish stricter safety standards for batteries and products containing them for both manufacturers and consumers, let's learn about the "Global Awareness Campaign on Lithium-ion Battery Product Safety" in 2024 of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development - OECD. This program has made a number of recommendations for both consumers and businesses in the process of purchasing and using lithium-ion batteries specifically as follows:

2. OECD consumer guide to the proper storage and use of lithium-ion batteries¹

Consumers need to read and follow the manufacturer's product instructions: Before using a lithium-ion battery-powered product, consumers should carefully read the manufacturer's instructions. Using the appropriate charger for the consumer's device will help prevent incidents that could cause a fire.

Check for information regarding product recall programs: Consumers should look for recall information on lithium-ion battery-powered products before purchasing to avoid unnecessary damage. Up-to-date recall information will help consumers make safer product choices, minimizing human and material damage.

Pay attention to monitor the device while charging and unplug when fully charged: consumers should not overcharge their devices as this can cause the internal temperature of the battery cells to rise. In addition, during charging, consumers should keep the charger away

¹ Nguồn: [Power your life. Safely. | OECD](#)

from flammable objects and regularly monitor the device to ensure that it does not overheat or show any other signs of abnormality.

Never use damaged or modified batteries: Consumers should immediately stop using the product containing the battery if they notice any abnormal signs such as damage, deformation, overheating, swelling or leakage. Consumers should also avoid using batteries, products or chargers that show signs of failure.

Recycle or dispose of batteries properly: When a lithium-ion battery-powered product is no longer needed, consumers should follow and comply with the manufacturer's and local government's recycling or disposal guidelines. Consumers are also encouraged to participate in recycling to promote sustainable production and consumption.

3. OECD guidance for businesses on ensuring consumer safety²

Failure to comply with safety regulations related to lithium-ion batteries can cause serious personal and property injuries, and businesses responsible for manufacturing and distributing products to consumers can result in fines, product bans, and negative reputational damage. To ensure product safety, businesses should follow the instructions, specifically as follows:

3.1. Provide only products that meet full safety standards

When selling products containing lithium-ion batteries, whether in physical stores or online platforms, businesses must ensure full compliance with the safety regulations as required by law in the country or region where the product is sold.

3.2. Stay up to date on product safety and recalls

Businesses should regularly monitor and update information on product recalls and related product safety bulletins and share this information with consumers. Organizations and individuals can refer to OECD product recall information to be proactive in ensuring consumer safety.

3.3. Check for warning signs on products containing lithium-ion batteries.

Businesses are responsible for checking the safety warnings displayed on products containing lithium-ion batteries before selling them to consumers. Clear, transparent information will help reduce the risk of fire or other incidents that cause harm to consumers.

3.4. Ensure that instructions on how to safely charge, store and dispose of batteries are provided to consumers

Businesses are responsible for providing consumers with detailed instructions on how to use, store and dispose of batteries properly at the point of sale. Clear and complete communication of product safety information not only helps to reduce the risk of incidents but also helps to prevent unnecessary accidents when using products containing lithium-ion batteries.

3.5. Share contact information and notify consumers of unsafe practices

Businesses selling products should designate personnel responsible for receiving and responding to consumer inquiries related to product safety, and encour-

age consumers to report any relevant concerns. In addition, businesses should use easily accessible contact methods to ensure convenience for consumers.

As soon as they receive information about product safety risks from manufacturers, specialized management agencies or feedback from customers, businesses selling products should promptly verify the information, conduct investigations and share verified information with the consumer community and relevant parties.

The risk of fire and explosion when using lithium-ion batteries is an issue that needs attention, especially as the number of products using lithium-ion batteries is increasing. Compliance with safety notes and instructions is extremely important to ensure the safety when using products with rechargeable lithium-ion batteries.

The above is some information from the 2024 "Global Awareness Campaign on Lithium-ion Battery Product Safety" implemented by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development - OECD. For more information about the above Campaign or OECD's policies and activities in the field of consumer protection, consumers and other relevant organizations and individuals can visit the OECD website at the following address: Information about the Campaign: <https://www.oecd.org/en/about/projects/power-your-life-safely.html>; or information about consumer-related policies: <https://www.oecd.org/en/topics/consumer-policy.html#related-policy-issues>.

4. Some recommendations for Vietnam from the Global Awareness Campaign on Lithium-ion Battery Product Safety

For consumers

From the content of the "Global Awareness Campaign on Lithium-ion Battery Product Safety" in 2024 launched by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development - OECD, based on reviewing the content on safety when using lithium-ion batteries in the Vietnamese market, we see that the benefits that lithium-ion batteries bring to consumers are numerous, however, there will also be many consequences if consumers do not use them properly according to the manufacturer's instructions and regulations on environmental protection, as well as manufacturers do not comply with product safety regulations for consumers and the manufacturer's responsibility in destroying and recycling lithium-ion batteries in the market, the following are some recommendations for relevant agencies and organizations that are similar and consistent with the regulations on consumer responsibility as prescribed in Clause 1, Clause 2, Clause 3, Article 5 of the Law on Consumer Protection 2023 on the responsibility of "Checking products and goods before receiving according to the provisions of law". law; choose to consume products and goods with clear origin; Consumption does not violate the law, does not go against good customs and social ethics, does not infringe on national, ethnic, public interests, does not cause harm to the life, health, property of oneself and others; Comply with the conditions, instructions for transporting, preserving, us-

² [Power your life. Safely. | OECD](https://www.oecd.org/en/about/projects/power-your-life-safely.html)

ing products, goods, services; regulations on inspection, environmental protection, sustainable consumption according to the provisions of law”.

The content of recommendations on recycling or disposing of batteries properly is also consistent with the provisions of the law on protection of consumer rights in terms of sustainable consumption. This is a new content included in the Law on Consumer Protection in 2023, effective from July 1, 2024. The OECD's guidelines for consumers on lithium-ion batteries are very useful, suitable and similar to current regulations in Vietnam, especially on how to safely use and dispose of or recycle used lithium-ion batteries to ensure environmental safety.

For manufacturers

In the context of global economic cooperation, a business that produces goods and services not only supplies products to the domestic market but also supplies products to the international market. Therefore, a business that provides goods and services must not only meet the regulations and standards of Vietnam and the regulations of the country to which the business's products are intended to be supplied.

OECD guidelines for businesses relate to the provision of products that meet safety standards to the market, or the responsibility to provide information related to the responsibility to recall defective goods, the responsibility to guide and warn consumers during the use of goods and services, as well as instructions on how to act when batteries are not safe. OECD's guidelines for businesses in the process of supplying goods and products to the market are also consistent with the provisions on business responsibilities under the provisions of the Law on Consumer Protection in 2023, specifically responsibilities related to the responsibility of ensuring safety, measurement, quantity, volume, quality, and uses of products, goods, and services sold and provided to consumers in Article 14, the responsibility of providing information about products, goods, services, standard contracts, and general transaction conditions for consumers in Article 21, and the responsibility for liability for defective products and goods in Articles 32 and 33 of the Law. In addition, according to the provisions of Article 55 of the Law on Environmental Protection in 2020, it stipulates the responsibility of organizations and individuals producing and importing waste, including battery waste. However, OECD regulations and recommendations for businesses supplying

lithium-ion batteries to the market are stricter and compliance requirements are higher.

For state management agencies

State management agencies need to step up the implementation of the Law on Consumer Protection in 2023, the Law on Environmental Protection in 2020, increase propaganda for consumers and the business community to fulfill the responsibilities of manufacturers as well as ensure safety during use, limit industrial waste to the environment. Both consumers and manufacturers need to strictly comply with regulations on waste disposal and collection for reuse of lithium-ion battery waste, which both contributes to environmental protection and increases the value of products.

Vietnam's international economic integration process is increasingly strong, which creates opportunities for deep economic, political and social cooperation. Enterprises are facilitated to expand their sales markets, markets that are not only limited to Vietnam but also developed markets, requiring high quality goods and services as well as high environmental responsibilities such as the US, Japan, and Europe. To be successful in selling goods and services in developed markets, Vietnamese businesses need to comply with legal regulations, including regulations on lithium-ion battery product safety. The content of the Global Awareness Campaign on Lithium-ion Battery Product Safety 2024 of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development is very important for consumers as well as businesses operating in the field of lithium-ion battery production to ensure safety for the production and business environment as well as environmental safety in general.

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